

Studies on metal complexes of quinazoly Schiff bases

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The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pd^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 3-amino-2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-one and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been prepared and characterised by physico-chemical data. All the three ligands behave as uninegative, bidentate towards Pd^{II} coordinating through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen and as uninegative, tridentate towards the other metal ions with additional coordination through thioketo sulphur. The geometry and the bonding characteristics associated with the complexes have been deduced from the electronic and ESR spectral data.

Quinazoline derivatives, particularly those which are 2,3-disubstituted ones, are biologically active and find application in medicinal use¹. Despite the ligational potentiality associated with quinazoline derivatives, the studies made on the metal complexes of these compounds are limited. For this reason, we report, herein, the synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pd^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of quinazoly Schiff bases namely 3-(2'-hydroxybenzalamino)-2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-one (HBAMQ), 3-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzalamino)-2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-one (HMAMQ) and 3-(2'-hydroxynaphthalamino)-2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-one (HNAMQ) (1).

Ar = 2-OHC₆H₄, 2-OH-3-OMeC₆H₃, 2-OHC₁₀H₆

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Results and discussion

All the metal complexes (Table 1) are coloured, stable at room temperature and are non-hygroscopic. Upon heating, they decompose without melting above 200°. The complexes are insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol and acetone and fairly soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. All the metal complexes show residual conductance values (9–14 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMF indicating that they are non-electrolytes². The magnetic moment data indicate that Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of all the three ligands are paramagnetic to the extent of three, two and one unpaired electrons respectively and that Zn^{II} , Pd^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

A sharp band corresponding to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ of quinazoline ring observed around 1680 cm^{-1} in the ligands is not lower shifted in their metal complexes indicating non-involvement of oxygen of this group in coordination³. The ligands do not reveal a band in the range 2600–2550 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{S}-\text{H}$, suggesting that this group has undergone tautomerism into thione forms⁴. Further, the ligands show four bands in the regions 1530–1526 (band I), 1398–1385 (band II), 1026–978 (band III) and 772–736 (band IV) cm^{-1} having contributions respectively from ($\delta \text{C}-\text{H} + \delta \text{N}-\text{H}$), ($\nu \text{C}=\text{S} + \nu \text{C}=\text{N} + \delta \text{C}-\text{H}$), ($\delta \text{C}-\text{N} + \nu \text{C}-\text{S}$) and $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ vibration modes of thioamide ($\text{H}-\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{S}$) group^{5,6}. In all the metal complexes excepting those of Pd^{II} , all the thioamide bands, with an exception of band I, have shifted to lower frequencies indicating coordination through sulphur⁵. The ligands, still further, record small intensity bands in the region 3455–3200 cm^{-1} , the one at higher frequency due to $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ and the other at lower frequency due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$. The higher frequency band disappears whereas the lower frequency one persists at the same or appears at higher frequency in the complexes. This indicates that the oxygen of *o*-hydroxy group is involved in complexation through deprotonation and that the nitrogen of $\text{N}-\text{H}$ is not⁷. A medium intensity band that makes its presence in the ligands around 1600 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ has been found lower shifted by about 30 cm^{-1} in all the complexes suggesting the involvement of nitrogen of this group in coordination⁸. In addition, the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes display medium or low intensity bands around 1540, 1440 and 1310 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and δCH_3 vibrations of the coordinated acetate ion⁹. Thus, the ligands act as uninegative, bidentate ones towards Pd^{II} coordinating through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen and as mononegative, tridentate ones towards the other metal ions

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of metal complexes*

Metal complex	Colour	Metal (%): Found (calcd.)	Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Mustard yellow	8.82 (9.05)	12	4.79
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Yellow	8.88 (9.01)	10	3.24
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Dark green	9.54 (9.68)	10	1.84
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Pale yellow	15.16 (15.54)	14	—
$\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Brick red	14.95 (15.22)	9	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Pale yellow	24.22 (24.03)	12	—
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})_2$	Dark brown	8.07 (8.28)	12	4.83
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})_2$	Yellow	8.13 (8.25)	11	3.21
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})_2$	Dark green	8.65 (8.87)	10	1.82
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Pale yellow	14.76 (14.50)	12	—
$\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})_2$	Light brown	14.14 (14.02)	10	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Light yellow	22.24 (22.58)	12	—
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Brown	7.72 (7.84)	12	4.80
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Yellow	7.65 (7.81)	10	3.20
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Dark green	8.28 (8.40)	12	1.83
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Pale yellow	13.64 (13.88)	10	—
$\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$	Brick red	13.08 (13.31)	9	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S})(\text{OAc})$	Pale yellow	21.51 (21.70)	10	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

with additional coordination through thioketo sulphur.

The present Co^{II} complexes each show three peaks around 9250 (ν_1), 16150 (ν_2) and 23000 (ν_3) cm^{-1} assignable respectively to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ of octahedral geometry¹⁰. Similarly, the Ni^{II} complexes each give three peaks around 9300 (ν_1), 13900 (ν_2) and 23800 (ν_3) cm^{-1} that could be assigned respectively to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ of octahedral geometry¹¹. The Racah interelectronic repulsion pa-

rameter (B), ligand field splitting energy ($10 Dq$) and nephelauxetic parameter (β) for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have been evaluated¹² (Table 2). Based on the values observed, the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes may be arranged with respect to orbital overlap and extent of covalency as

(where M = Co, Ni)

The Cu^{II} complexes show each two somewhat broad peaks around 15600 and 19950 cm^{-1} assignable respectively

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes

Metal complex	Frequency cm ⁻¹			B cm ⁻¹	10 Dq cm ⁻¹	β
	ν ₁	ν ₂	ν ₃			
Co(BAMQ) ₂	9260	16130	23095	763	6870	0.786
Co(MAMQ) ₂	9200	16050	23200	777	6852	0.800
Co(NAMQ) ₂	9300	16220	22980	753	6918	0.775
Ni(BAMQ) ₂	9430	14090	23810	641	9430	0.622
Ni(MAMQ) ₂	9270	14010	23950	677	9270	6.657
Ni(NAMQ) ₂	9310	13700	23660	629	9310	0.611

to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. These observations, coupled with other data suggest a tetragonal geometry for the complexes¹³. The present Pd^{II} complexes show each three peaks around 14650, 17850 and 22700 cm⁻¹ that could be assigned, in the order given, to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ of square-planar geometry¹⁴. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes show no *d-d* bands in their electronic spectra and on the basis of other data obtained, they have been assigned tetrahedral geometry.

The ESR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes are anisotropic in nature in that each of them has two peak envelopes, one of small intensity appearing as shoulders towards low field and the other of large intensity towards high field. The small intensity envelope has been resolved into three or four segments due to Cu ($I = 3/2$) hyperfine interaction while the large intensity one remains unresolved. The ESR parameters for the complexes have been calculated using appropriate method and equations^{15(a,b)} and are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. ESR data of Cu^{II} complexes

Metal complex	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$A_{ } \times 10^4$ cm ⁻¹	α^2	β^2	γ^2
Cu(BAMQ) ₂	2.28	2.07	2.14	84	0.86	0.76	0.94
Cu(MAMQ) ₂	2.28	2.05	2.13	90	0.88	0.74	0.79
Cu(NAMQ) ₂	2.26	2.04	2.11	80	0.77	0.79	0.59

In all the cases, it is found that $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > 2$ indicating that the unpaired electron lies in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital with ${}^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state – a characteristic of elongated octahedral geometry¹⁶. The α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 values for the complexes are in the ranges 0.77–0.88, 0.74–0.79 and 0.59–0.94 suggesting appreciable/moderate in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding and out-of-plane π -bonding respectively^{15(b)}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R or B.D.H. grade. 3-Amino-2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-ones (i) was pre-

pared as reported earlier¹⁷. The ligands HBAMQ, HMAMQ and HNAMQ were prepared by refluxing equimolar methanolic solutions of (i) and the respective aldehydes in presence of a few drops of piperidine for 3 h. The solids that separated during reflux were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallized from hot dry methanol. The colour, yield (%), m.p. (°C) and elemental analysis (%) of HBAMQ, HMAMQ and HNAMQ are : yellow, 78, 190 (Found : C, 60.26; H, 3.69; N, 14.02. C₁₅H₁₁N₃O₂S requires : C, 60.59; H, 3.74; N, 14.14%); white, 86, 240 (Found : C, 58.48; H, 3.93; N, 12.69. C₁₆H₁₃N₃O₃S requires : C, 58.70; H, 4.01; N, 12.84%) and mustard yellow, 82, 228 (Found : C, 65.39; H, 3.67; N, 11.98. C₁₉H₁₃N₃O₂S requires : C, 65.68; H, 3.78; N, 12.10%). Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes were prepared taking respective metal acetates and Pd^{II} complexes using metal chloride. In the preparation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes, the metal and the ligand were combined in 1 : 2 mole ratio, while in the case of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes they were mixed in 1 : 1 ratio using methanol or water for the metal salts and methanol-DMF (20 : 1) mixture for the ligands. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for about 3 h, the solid that separated was filtered, washed with water, hot methanol and ether and dried in air.

The elemental analyses were carried out by C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductance measurements were made in DMF at 10⁻³ M concentration on a Digisun digital conductivity meter, DI 909 model. Gouy balance calibrated with Hg[Co(NCS)₄] was used to measure the magnetic susceptibility of the metal complexes at room temperature. The IR spectra of the ligands and the metal complexes in KBr were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using JASCO FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the metal complexes in DMF were recorded on JASCO 7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The Varian E-4 X-band spectrophotometer operating in the frequency range 8.8–9.6 GHz available with R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Chennai was employed in recording the ESR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes in DMF solution at LNT. The metal content in the complexes, after decomposition with conc. HNO₃, was determined by standard procedures – Cu by iodometry, Ni and Pd by gravimetry and Co, Zn and Cd by complexometry¹⁸.

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References

1. W. Merilus, *J. Med Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 171; S. K. Saxena and S. Somasekhara, *J. Indian Med. Res.*, 1972, **60**, 284; V. Alagarsamy, U. S. Pathak and R. K. Goyal, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, **1**, 63; V. Alagarsamy, U. S. Pathak, D. Sriram, S. N. Pandeya and E. De Clereq, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, **6**, 433.
2. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
3. S. K. Sengupta and Nizamuddin, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 426.
4. K. Nakanishi and P. H. Solomon, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Holden-Day Inc., 1977, p. 50.
5. B. Singh and U. Agarwala, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 2341.
6. B. Singh and K. P. Thakur, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1735.
7. A. Sammour, A. F. M. Fammy and M. Mahmoud, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **13**, 272.
8. R. L. Dutta and A. K. Sarkar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 57.
9. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1978, p. 231.
10. Mathews and R. A. Walton, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1443.
11. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, 1984, p. 507.
12. A. B. P. Lever, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1966, **45**, 711; C. K. Jorgenson, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **4**, 73.
13. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, 1984, pp. 557, 565.
14. P. D. Goggin, R. J. Goodfellow and F. J. S. Read, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1298.
15. (a) F. K. Kneubuhl, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, **33**, 1074; (b) S. G. Kulkarni, D. V. Jahagirdar and D. D. Khanolkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 251.
16. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 2nd. ed., Affiliated East-west Press Pvt. Ltd., 1993, pp. 223, 224.
17. V. Alagarsamy, U. S. Pathak and R. K. Goyal, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, 63.
18. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, 3rd. ed., 1961, pp. 351, 479, 512, 443, 444.